

Book Review: Till Bardoux's translation of Anders Engberg-Pedersen's *Martial Aesthetics: How War Became an Art Form*

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Bardoux, Till, trans. Engberg-Pedersen, Anders, ed. *Martial Aesthetics: How War Became an Art Form*. Göttingen: Wallstein Verlag, 2024. ISBN 978-3-8353-9176-5. Pp. 205, 14 partly color illus. Hardcover €30.00.

Anders Engberg-Pedersen's *Martial Aesthetics: How War Became an Art Form* provides a detailed history of the complex relationship between war, art, and science, primarily from the Thirty Years' War in Germany to the present day. Albrecht von Wallenstein, immortalized in Friedrich Schiller's play *Wallenstein*, serves as the starting point for an analysis of military decision-making based on various forms of contingency media. Negative examples for contingency narratives are forms of group-related misanthropy, such as antisemitism.

Media such as literature, histories, chess, and modern war games,

as well as state-of-the-art simulations, have served the purpose of creating positive, goal-related contingency in the military and are analyzed here with respect to their individual and overall potential.

Engberg-Pedersen illustrates the connections between aesthetics, media, and military theory in a chronological yet interconnected, cohesive rhetorical approach. Chapters and thoughts build upon each other and are connected through cross-references, which enhance the reader's comprehension. He questions whether war is an art form and how modern operationalization of the creative sphere, such as mili-

tary design, leads to the promised success in the chaotic *Kriegstheater* on the 21st-century war stage. The felicitous translation into German by Till Bardoux comes just in time for recipients from the Bundeswehr, which celebrates its 70th anniversary on November 12, 2025.

The monograph consists of five chapters, an introduction, and an epilogue. References to artist and theorist Hakun Farocki, who explored the epistemological boundaries of military simulations and their impact on soldiers in his work, and Walter Benjamin's well-known essay "The Artwork in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction" outline the problem. Benjamin described how fascist aesthetics constituted both itself and European fascism under the given circumstances of technical reproduction through mass media, especially pointing out the role of militarized thinking. A political dimension is given through General James Norman Mattis' structural decision-making, which led to a new form of creative warfare. A brief overview of the topic of martial aesthetics follows.

The first chapter, "Astrological War Media," transports the reader back to 17th-century Germany, where General Albrecht von Wallenstein faces a problem that confronts military leaders today: selecting the most effective military strategy. He is indecisive and decides at last to rely on a *speculum astrologicum*, a specific sort of horoscope that promises to predict the future.

This pre-stage of scientifically based forecasting, best compared to

"Strategic Foresight Analysis" that is part of NATO's Strategic Warfare Development Command today, is a historically outstanding example of prediction and preparation for military scenarios. Outstanding, because it is on the border of overcoming clairvoyance during the Enlightenment. This early military futurology is situated within a broader historical context. Engberg-Pedersen teaches us about astrologically based futurology in the ancient world, as well as the interplay between doubt and action in Greek philosophy, particularly with Aristotle. The theory of possible worlds from Leibniz, Immanuel Kant's *The Critique of Judgement*, and Friedrich Schiller's aesthetic writings, which are based on the former, are called into play to give an overall view of aesthetic theory in the given time. Furthermore, the history of the murdered General Wallenstein, its fictional counterpart in the form of Schiller's play, and, thirdly, the juxtaposition of astrological contingency media, aesthetic philosophy, and a war philosophical debate on the power of imagined and unimagined martial worlds yield the content of this chapter. Engberg-Pedersen illustrates a dense and complex crosspoint of aesthetic and military thinking during the Enlightenment, which has effects today.

The next chapter, "The Artifact of War," builds upon the complex of martial world-making by giving a history of the origin of war games. A detailed intellectual history is supplemented by outstanding developments in this field, such as Johann Hellwig's *Attempt of a Tactical Game based upon Chess* from 1780. The chapter helps us understand

the history of the war game within the context of 17th-century debates on aesthetics and the role of play in education, while early debates on whether war games should train emotions or not are described.

Quite well-known is the concept of “Homo Ludens” by Joseph Huizinga for every scholar that had been busy with game theory. In contrast, the line drawn from Leibniz’s idea of possible worlds in combination with his Theodizee to Huizinga’s concept leads Engberg-Pedersen to a convincing argument. In short, the war game places players, such as officers in training, in the role of the rather aesthetically operating demiurge of the war theater to come. Furthermore, the future violence on the real battlefield is to some degree fictionalized. This aesthetic effort enables the regulation of affect and fosters strong leadership, which is demanded by the reality of warfare.

The reader, who might be seduced to an imagination of an *optimum bellum* himself, is humbled as a mortal being with epistemological boundaries that are, for instance, set in the prediction of future events. Simulating the perfect warfare, as it was imagined in the Prussian era with those “artifacts of war”, was only possible because of the first ideas of autonomy and entelechic worlds in the humanities and arts.

How those “artifacts of war” can be categorized is the initial question of Chapter Three, “Operational Aesthetics”. A timeline of early digital war simulations and games is narrated and contextualized, and eventually put into

perspective by Alexander Baumgarten, a pioneer in aesthetic research and the development of aesthetics as an autonomous discipline. The diversion of aesthetic and philosophical thinking is compared with the technical results of soldiers being taught about warfare with personal computers that run simulations. The cognitive and aesthetic training of the “felix aestheticus in uniform” (p. 79) is unraveled through a history of science, enlightening the reader about the processes he might have undergone due to the omnipresence of martial aesthetics.

The argument seems to be interrupted with Chapter Four, “The War Artists,” but reveals both a recourse and more than a digression in the train of thought of the author. Here, we learn in detail about the debate presented in Chapter Two: whether war is an art form or a science. Equations of military leaders as dramaturges, conductors, or directors of artworks are critically reflected. The necessity for understanding the ontological line between war and art, and war and playing, becomes clear at this point and yields a brief history of bad ideas.

The second iteration of the attempted amalgamation of artistic activities and the conduct of warfare is explained in the last chapter titled “Designing War.” Once more, the reader is confronted with General Mattis’ Memorandum Assessment of Effects-Based Operations, after it had been mentioned in the previous chapter. This preview concludes here with a critique of Military Design. The objectively written

historiography of Military Design ranges from sociological System Theory to “Systemic Operational Design”, from “Campaign Design” to “Army Design Methodology”, and others. Readers of *Martial Aesthetics* learn that all of the mentioned reach back to Design Thinking developed in the past century. Therefore, in a long range, contemporary Military Design can be traced back to Prussian perspectives on war as a form of art, raising awareness for the fact that “as it transfigures violence into artistic matter, military design frames war not as a brutal act of military force and a means of last resort but as a virtuous and even desirable activity to be pursued for its own sake.” (p.145). The shown problems that occur with the implementation of Military Design, such as little to no decrease in civilian victims or lowering of costs, leave the reader in doubt of the sense of Military Design, especially with respect to the shown dangers of transfiguring war as an art form.

The Epilogue implements the argument on the last failed operation in Afghanistan. While the country is suppressed by the Taliban right now, the newest technologies that reproduce the military operational area could not prevent the disaster of troop withdrawal from Kabul. According to Engberg-Pedersen, a central fallacy was the idea that contingency media could overcome the chaos and complexity of warfare, thereby rendering the unexpected completely unexpected. The

simulations were unable to prevent the disaster of the evacuation. I simply want to repeat the dedication of the book to Reporting Officer Mette Teilmann Nielsen, who was murdered by the Taliban while serving the European Union Police Mission in Kabul, Afghanistan, on 17 January 2014, in the presence of her colleague Simon Chase and 19 other people, to express my commiseration.¹

Having read both the translation and the original as a native speaker of German, I evaluate Till Bardoux’s work as excellent. The translated work reads just as well as the English original. Currently enrolled as a PhD student, I perceived Engberg-Pedersen’s monograph as a partly challenging yet certainly worthwhile lecture, which offers space for subsequent research or simply philosophical contemplation on warfare. The outlined ethical problems are certainly worth reflecting on by both scholars of war studies and cultural/literary studies, but could have been given more attention. Finally, this work is itself a contribution in the sense of Γνώθι σεαυτόν (Gnothi seauton, know thyself) popular in the enlightenment, which helps to recognize oneself as a militarized subject. The ethically interested soldier, military leader or researcher should read *Martial Aesthetics*.

¹ European External Action Service. We remember fallen colleagues. Accessed August 13, 2025. https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/we-remember-fallen-colleagues_en.

About the Author

Axel Grimmeißer is a PhD student at the University of Augsburg (Germany); Research interests in war literature, literature of exile, military ethics, Just War Theory, War, Philosophy, Extremism, Antisemitism, Conflict Studies, Peace Studies, intellectual history, narrative warfare, terrorism. He studied German language and literature, with a minor in Philosophy, at the University of Augsburg (Germany).

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Thesis on the autobiography of German writer Andreas Maier and its use of the metaphor of the Möbius Strip for group formations. Followed by a Master's in the Elite-Course of Study Ethics of textcultures at the Universities of Augsburg and Erlangen, offered by the Elite-Network of Bavaria. Works, e.g., on right-wing extremism in theater, the cultural history of the labyrinth, and German post-war literature. Thesis inter alia on Didier Eribon's *Retour à Reims*, an autobiographical reflection on the far left and far right. Reims is a French city where the capitulation of the Wehrmacht was signed on May 7, 1945.

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